

Kaleshwaram

A new paradigm in water resources development

The report identifies and touches upon aspects that have worked collectively to bring the required value and make a success story through Kaleshwaram Lift Irrigation Project. The report deep dives into the project's potential and its possible impact on the process of deepening development by upstreaming water.

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1. Introduction

Identifying solutions to developmental problems is one of the critical requirements of governance in any country. There have been persistent problems with socioeconomic inequalities, climate change and environmental fragility, poverty, and unemployment, among others, in many parts of the world. To think of a solution to these global problems is a herculean policy task. We often come across initiatives by various countries addressing specific challenges to development through technological interventions combined with visionary leadership (e.g., water problems in Israel, Sweden's renewable electricity, South Korea's healthcare systems, besides others) The UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) developed frameworks for the countries to address some of these challenges through partnership mode. With the availability of such parameters and to create the required developmental impact, a leadership which could think big to connect the dots along with an appropriate triggering point could show the way to accelerate more profound development.

The State Government of Telangana, since its formation in 2014, identified access to water as the main triggering point to deepen development. Anticipating that water availability for all could be an excellent sustainable developmental strategy for the newly carved semi-arid state, especially when agriculture and its allied activities are the primary sources of income for most¹, strengthened a case for Kaleshwaram Lift Irrigation in the days to come.

There is a close connection between water and economic development. Considering the socio-economic inequalities and unequal growth patterns in the Telangana region, it makes a case for the redistribution of water. It is predicted that access to water will help eradicate poverty and enable sustained economic growth. Good management of water resources brings more certainty and efficiency in productivity across economic sectors and contributes to the ecosystem's health.

This report details an innovative approach to larger developmental objectives adopted by the State of Telangana. Upon its formation as the 29th Indian State², the think tank and the leadership took the case of making water available to all (as in, no one is left behind!) as the core of sustainable development. Water can potentially provide societies with tremendous social, economic and environmental benefits. Telangana's uneven geography, semi-arid landscape, and heavy dependence on rainwater & groundwater for agriculture have impacted its growth trajectory. The Kaleshwaram Lift Irrigation Project was presented as a solution to this persistent problem. This dream project addressed all three 'I's of sustainable development – Infrastructure development, Inclusive Growth, and Innovation. The idea of kaleshwaram is conceived in such a way that it would lead to a decentralized infrastructure development process. The upland population of Telangana, who are mostly tribal and backward class, will get an opportunity to get better moving closer to inclusive growth. Kaleshwaram also helps in realising inclusive growth, as it is designed in such a way that the lower class and tribal population of Telangana, who are mostly found in uplands, will get an opportunity to get better. The new state was upfront in using the latest technologies and innovations

¹ Though most of the GSDP comes from the State's service sector due to IT boom, a large number of population depend on Agriculture for their growth and livelihood.

² After Jammu & Kashmir was made a Union Territory, Telangana is now the 28th State under the Indian Union.

to achieve this important milestone. All the three 'I's are covered in different sub-headings throughout the report. However, it is too early to claim Kaleshwaram's impact on development through the three 'I's.

The report identifies and touches upon aspects that have worked collectively to bring the required value and make a success story through Kaleshwaram Lift Irrigation Project. The report deep dives into the project's potential and impact on the deepening development process by upstreaming water.

2. Making Water a part of Economic Development

Human civilisations worldwide evolved around the waters, popularly known as river valley civilisations³. The availability of drinking water and the surrounding fertile landscape powered these civilisations to flourish and start a social life. Henceforth, water became a key contributor to economic development and social progress, leading to increased populations and greater economic activities. Although population growth, technical progress and an expanded scale of economic activities have made it necessary and possible for the dispersal of human settlements and their economic activities away from river valleys, their dependence on water has never declined but increased manifold instead (Saleth, 2002). Water played a vital role in the divide between poverty and prosperity. Development naturally happens in regions with water, but the challenge is developing regions with a scanty natural flow of water.

When we look at the global water distribution, we only have 2% fresh water (98% salt/sea water). Of that 2%, 87% is locked up in ice and glaciers, 12% is groundwater, and only 1% (300 cubic miles, which is about 1/10,000 of the 1% of total water) is the surface water source as rivers and lakes (School of Natural Resources, University of Nebraska- Lincoln, n.d.). Pressure on this one per cent of surface water (also known as blue water) is likely to worsen with population growth, climate changes, and unplanned development, among others, degrading the quality and raising the cost of its treatment, thus threatening the ecosystem and human health (Palaniappan et al., 2010).

It is observed that the positive relationship between water resources and economic development is increasingly strained in developing countries and even in developed countries. The negative impacts include ecological and social disturbances in project areas, salinity in irrigated regions, aquifer depletion in arid zones, pollution-induced water quality, and health damages in urban centres, thus raising social costs. In contrast, inefficient usage and mismanagement reduce the social benefits of the additional water supply. As a result, water resources' net economic and welfare contributions tend to decline over time and across countries. The urgent challenge facing nations today is to find ways to improve the financial and economic performance of the water sector in order to enhance and sustain its indispensable contributions to socio-economic development.

³ Tigris River (Mesopotamian civilization), Nile River (Egyptian civilization), Yellow River (Chinese civilization) and Indus River (Indus Valley civilization), among others.

One of the major reasons for the unequal use of water resources is because of its spatial distribution. For instance, Brazil, with just a fraction of the global population share, has one-fifth of global fresh water resources. In contrast, India and China, sharing over a third of the world population, have only a tenth (Shiklomanov, 1993, p.3). The issue will still be more complicated as the extent of future utilization of even this accessible blue water⁴ is also threatened by climatic change-induced variations in the level and spatial pattern of global temperature and precipitation (Gleick, 1993).

Every country has a system to manage its water for development. There are some excellent practices from which one could learn. For example, Israel has 60% desert, and the rest is semi-arid. Since its foundation in 1948, Israel's population has grown tenfold because of the mass immigration of Jews post WW-II. Its annual rainfall is not so generous; it has a challenging climate and an unforgiving landscape. Despite these limitations, it does not have a water crisis. On the contrary, it has a water surplus and even exports water to some of its neighboring countries. It happened purely because of water planning and technological solutions central to the country at every stage of its development (Siegel, 2015). The former head of the Israel Water Commission, Shimon Tal, once said: "You can tell a lot about a country by the way it manages its water" (Siegel, 2015, p. 6). Indeed, there is a lot of meaning in this statement.

To understand the correlation between water and development, two important aspects need to be considered and understood as to how the nations deal with them. First, the extent of dependence of agricultural production on rainwater, and second, the groundwater extraction for agriculture and industrial use.

Rainfall, in many cases, has high predictive value for economic growth mainly because the agriculture sector is the lifeline for a good percentage of the workforce worldwide, more so for developing countries. Any significant deviations from average rainfall adversely affect the earning potential of these workers, which in turn depresses private consumption. Rainfall remains vital to agricultural productivity due to the pervasive scarcity of water supply (World Bank Group, 2018). Around 52% of the overall cropped area in India still needs irrigation, with certain regions being chronically water-stressed (Mishra, 2017).

The Indian economy is uniquely reliant on rainfall. It is vital for the livelihood of much of India's 1.3 billion population as it plays a crucial role in determining the productivity of the agriculture sector. The agriculture sector employs around 47% of the workforce, occupies 60% of the country's land, and uses 90% of its water resources (World Bank Group, 2018). India presently ranks among the world's most water-stressed countries. Water scarcity in India makes the agriculture sector highly susceptible to volatile monsoons. The relationship between rainfall, climate, and economic growth is examined by vast literature (Dell et al., 2014). Some studies point out that a 1% increase in rainfall in India relative to its mean is correlated with a 0.16% increase in GDP growth (Virmani, 2006; Gadgil & Gadgil, 2006). Hence, at the policy level, exploring options to delink rainfall and economic growth is essential.

⁴ Blue water is the water in our surface and groundwater reservoirs.

The second aspect connected to development is the use and misuse of groundwater. Groundwater is an indispensable resource for irrigation in many pockets of hard rock areas (HRAs), especially where there are no flows of perennial rivers.

According to International Water Management Institute (IWMI) (2010), over 80% of irrigated agriculture in India is currently supported by groundwater. India has 25 million pumps with almost a million added every year. In India, the rights to groundwater belong to the landowner as groundwater is attached to the land (Indian Easement Act, 1882).

There is theoretically no limitation on the volume of groundwater extraction by a landowner. Hence it cannot be an open-access resource. This resulted in the increase of irrigation pump sets in India from 0.15 million in the 1950s to around 19 million by 2000 and is annually pumping 220-230 billion m³, twice that of the USA and six times that of Western Europe, ascending as the world's largest extractor of groundwater. There has been an exponential growth in groundwater extraction from 37% in 1998 to 58% in 2010, pumping an average of 75 acre-inch of groundwater per annum, with the number of wells rising from 0.1 million in 1960 to 25 million in 2010. Hence, exploring options to delink economic growth and development associated with groundwater at the policy level is essential.

Dependency on rainfalls and groundwater for agricultural needs could be reduced by enhancing access to surface water. Lifting of water to the uplands has emerged as a viable option.

The skewed rainfall distribution and groundwater depletion hinder growth and development in the country. The construction of dams became a vital method to deepen development in water-scarce areas. Dams have significantly contributed to human development, and their benefits have been considerable. Dams were built to provide water for irrigation, domestic or industrial use, generate hydropower or help control floods. But they have their drawbacks, as they divert river flows, affecting the existing rights of people and their access to water, significantly impacting the environment (World Commission on Dams, 2000). There is hardly any case of a multipurpose dam and lift irrigation that offered a win-win situation. It has always been a zero-sum game. It will be interesting to see where Kaleshwaram Multipurpose lift irrigation stands out in this regard.

3. The political economy of lifting water: theory and practice

The history of irrigation dates back at least 8,000 years. The earliest known irrigation systems originated in Egypt and Mesopotamia in 6,000 B.C. Fighting against the flooding of the Nile several months each year, ancient civilisations pioneered a technique to divert flood waters to nearby crop fields, thereby utilising excess flood water for crops that would otherwise be difficult to grow due to lack of resources (World Commission on Dams, 2000).

This ancient technique is credited as the basis for agricultural economies and societies across the world. As a process of applying controlled amounts of water to plants at needed intervals, irrigation aids in growing crops and maintaining vegetation in a way that conserves water, preserves soil nutrients and saves time and energy (World Commission on Dams, 2000). The next level of this ancient technique is to lift water upstream, which indeed is a remarkable achievement.

Traditionally, irrigation depended on the natural flow of water, but modern irrigation is technology oriented and has a larger ambit which is not dependent on the natural flow of water. It must have been hard to imagine water going upwards in the absence of the advent of disruptive technologies. A large-scale lift irrigation system is one such innovation. Lift irrigation is a method of irrigation in which water, instead of being transported by natural flow (as in gravity-fed canal systems) requires external energy through fuel-based or electric power. It uses pumps or other mechanical means to take water to areas where water cannot go due to gravity. The practice of rising water is known as lift irrigation.

Modern irrigation systems have evolved to include reservoirs, tanks and wells, with reservoirs collecting water from natural sources such as lakes and rainwater runoff. As our global agricultural output continues to rise, irrigation protects against droughts and famines, ensuring successful and widespread crop yields (World Commission on Dams, 2000).

Theoretically, irrigation projects, including large dams, as defined by World Commission on Dams (WCD), are a nested set of sub-systems involving the dams as a source of supply, the irrigation system (including canals and on-farm irrigation application technology), the agricultural system (including crop production processes), and the wider rural socio-economic system and agricultural markets (World Commission on Dams, 2000, p. 42). The report also identifies the potential performance indicators for these large dam irrigation projects:

- ▶ Physical performance on water delivery area irrigated and cropped intensity.
- ▶ Cropping patterns and yields, as well as the value of production; and
- ▶ Net financial and economic benefits.

Financial and economic profitability became important (though may not be dominant), decision criteria in most of the water projects in developing countries. Consequently, approval of many large dam projects was contingent upon estimates of their predicted profitability. The measures typically used to assess profitability are the financial internal rate of return (FIRR)⁵ and economic internal rate of return (EIRR)⁶ as determined through cost-benefit analysis. Sometimes it may happen that the rate of return of a project may fall short of its target but still exceed the opportunity cost of capital to the economy. WCD Knowledge Base (2000) suggests that an EIRR of over 10% is judged acceptable in the context of a developing country⁷.

⁵ FIRR indicates if the project is profitable.

⁶ EIRR indicates if the project improves the overall economic welfare of the nation/state/region.

⁷ World Bank funds such projects if the EIRR is either 10% or more. For ADB funding it is 13% or more.

Analysts can gauge the merits of water resource projects by examining the ratio of benefits to costs (McKean, 1967). It is observed that if the ratio of benefits to cost is greater than 1, then the project should be allowed to proceed (assuming no mutually exclusive option with higher total net benefits) (Labhasetwar, 2013, p. 269). Labhasetwar (2013) also mentioned in his article that the Government of India preferred the voluntary application of cost-benefit analysis in evaluating water development projects instead of relying on it as a default starting point for decision-making (p. 269). While cost-benefit analysis has been used in the Environmental Impact Assessment Guidelines of water resources projects issued by the environment ministry, there is no evidence that cost-benefit analysis is used by government organizations in practice.

The last five decades have witnessed the development of the Lift Irrigation System, causing deep and far-reaching impact on the agricultural economy of the region. Lift irrigation projects often have a heavy capital outlay. India is leading in surface irrigation in the world. As of 2018, surface irrigation in India was 68,172 thousand ha which accounts to 26.65% of the world's surface irrigation.

The Kaleshwaram Multipurpose Lift Irrigation System, the largest in the world, is conceived to cater developmental needs of 13 of 33 districts in Telangana. In this context, the Kaleshwaram multipurpose lift irrigation project is valued as a consumption good (drinking water for Hyderabad and other cities, industrial use) and also as a productive input (agricultural produce). In 2016, the Environmental Protection and Training Research Institute (EPTRI) did a benefit-cost ratio analysis of the Kaleshwaram project. They gave a ratio of 1.55, which would mean that the benefits of the project exceed costs. In the subsequent sections, we will look into Kaleshwaram's size, scope and the trade-offs, but before that we would need to understand the topography, the historical background, and the socio-economic equations in the State of Telangana to visualise the importance of the project.

4. The Story of Telangana so far...

Telangana was formed on June 02, 2014, as the 29th state of the Indian Union. This happened after a prolonged struggle for separate statehood. The name "Telangana" refers to the word 'Trilinga Desa', earned due to the presence of three ancient Shiva Temples at Kaleshwaram, Srisailem, and Draksharamam (Telangana 360, n.d.).

Geographically, Hyderabad (under Nizams) commanded a pivotal position in the heart of India, with a population of nearly sixteen million and an area of 82,000 square miles. Hyderabad boasted of its own coinage, paper currency and stamps. Soon after the announcement of India's independence, Nizam declared his intention not to send representatives to the Constituent Assembly. The Indian Government refused to entertain a request that Hyderabad seeks a separate status, and Operation Polo was initiated to annex Hyderabad state. Hyderabad state's Kannada and Marathi-speaking areas merged with Karnataka and Maharashtra, respectively. At the same time, Telugu speaking region of Telangana was merged with Andhra state, with Hyderabad as the capital of the united Andhra Pradesh state in 1956. Although there was resentment against the merger, there was a period of calm.

A Gentleman's Agreement was signed on February 20, 1956, between Andhra Pradesh and Telangana leaders in 1956 before Andhra Pradesh State was formed (“Gentlemen's Agreement” of 1956, n.d.). The agreement provided safeguards with the purpose of preventing discrimination against Telangana by the government of Andhra Pradesh. As per the agreement, Telangana resources have to be utilised for the development of the region in accordance with the plans prepared by the representatives of the region. The then dominant thought process was that a larger state would have greater resources for faster development. However, the model of development adopted by the then administration mostly revolved around Hyderabad.

The violations of the Gentleman's Agreement are cited as one of the reasons for the formation of separate statehood for Telangana (Kodandaram, 2009). The journey of separate State as Telangana was not smooth, and it had its ups and down. The political aspirations of having a separate state of Telangana were growing strong, defeating all other interests.

The then leaders from the Telangana region felt the need for a separate focus for Telangana region, as the development was not deepening and is claimed that the resource allocation was skewed. Hence, a separate Telangana agitation was launched in 1969 but it could not sustain. The Telangana movement was given a final push by Shri. K Chandrasekhar Rao in 2001 with the formation of the TRS political party. Finally, a separate Telangana state was carved out in July 2013, and Telangana came into effect on June 2, 2014, as the 29th state of the Indian Union.

Indeed, one important aspect which triggered and strengthened the separate Telangana state movement was water distribution through irrigation. Here it is important to understand Telangana's topography.

Telangana comes under the northeastern part of the Deccan plateau in a semi-arid zone having an area of about 57,370 square miles (1,48,000 square kilometres). There are three river systems that cross Telangana – Godavari River takes a southeasterly course; Krishna river divides the peneplain into two regions; and Penneru river, flows in a northern direction. According to the Telangana State Climate Change Centre (TSCCC) (n.d.), Telangana's forests are mostly characterized as dry deciduous⁸ with reduced availability of surface water, which makes irrigation vital for agriculture in this region. Monsoon rains have been unevenly distributed, and 85% of the cultivated area in the region is rain-fed. Such a topography and rainfall pattern in Telangana has made Tank Irrigation ideal, which was followed historically in this region. The sheer number of inscriptions at tank sites and in temples proclaims the active role of Kakatiya, Qutubshahi and AsafJahi kings in the construction of tanks. In the state, about 46,531 minor irrigation sources are irrigating a total area of 10.17 lakh hectares (Kumar, 2017).

In the absence of proper availability of surface water across the region for agriculture, the tank system (minor irrigation) has been critical to the growth of agriculture in the state, contributing to soil and water conservation, flood control, drought mitigation, livestock and domestic uses, recharge of

⁸ According to Champion and Seth's classification, the Forests of the Telangana State fall under Dry Teak Forest, Southern Dry Mixed Deciduous Forest, Dry Deciduous Scrub, Dry Savannah Forest, Hardwickia Forest, Dry Bamboo Brakes, and Southern Thorn Forest.

groundwater, microclimate and protection of the environment. Access to irrigation infrastructure for the poor people allows them to enhance their crop production and broaden the opportunities to diversify their income base, reducing the vulnerability caused by the seasonality amidst the threats of climate change.

Given this scenario, it was observed by Kodandaram (2009) that the irrigation policies of Erstwhile Andhra Pradesh illustrated discrimination against the Telangana region. The then State Government prioritised Irrigation, constituting nearly 25% of total plan outlay between the 2nd five-year plan to the 9th five-year plan, which increased the net irrigated area from 27.47 lakh hectares to 55 lakh hectares between 1955 to 2001-02. As a consequence, net irrigated area increased from 27.47 lakh hectares to 55 lakh hectares between 1955-56 and 2001-02. However, the issue was that around 90% of this share went for large irrigation projects, which benefited Andhra region and the minor irrigation (Tank system) was highly neglected, which was indeed the lifeline for Telangana's agriculture. The large irrigation projects undertaken during Erstwhile Andhra Pradesh were often seen benefiting the Rayalaseema and coastal regions.

This policy has resulted in the decline of minor irrigation, particularly tank irrigation and consequently, the net area under tank irrigation declined from 10.68 lakh hectares to 5.67 lakh hectares between 1955-56 and 2001-02. In contrast, the net area irrigated by canals has increased from 12.92 lakh hectares to 15 lakh hectares between 1955- 56 and 2001-2002. The deterioration of the tank irrigation system has an adverse effect on Telangana more than the other regions because tanks have been the backbone of Telangana agriculture. Further, the loss of the area under the tank irrigation has yet to be compensated by the allocation of river waters.

On the other hand, the benefits of major irrigation have gone to coastal Andhra Pradesh. In 2003-04, 6.93 lakh hectares of area irrigated under canals were located in four coastal districts of the State - East Godavari, West Godavari, Krishna and Guntur. The corresponding figure for 2004-05 is 8.34 lakh hectares. Nearly 60 per cent of the net area irrigated under canals is located in these four districts, and the other 18 districts share 40 per cent. The neglect of irrigation in Telangana has forced the farmers in the region to rely more on well irrigation, impacting the groundwater table. Farmers have shifted to deep bore wells, which require energised motors to draw water. As a result, dependence on electricity has increased in the Telangana districts. All these have forced the farmers to invest massive amounts, from agriculture surpluses to secure irrigation facilities leading to a significant crisis in the region's agrarian economy. The state had a gap of almost 45% between irrigation potential created and utilised, primarily due to the need for more storage infrastructure.

The Coastal Andhra Pradesh is a major beneficiary of Godavari waters. The frequent failure of monsoons gives rise to the variability in rainfall of southern Telangana, often pushing the region into drought conditions occurring, on average, once in two and a half years. Many of the districts in Telangana are drought-prone, which include Mahabubnagar, Medak, Nizamabad, Ranga Reddy, Karimnagar, Nalgonda, and Warangal. The recurring drought in the absence of supplementing surface water leads farmers and wage earners into perpetual poverty and indebtedness. Eighty per

cent of farmer suicides in the erstwhile Andhra Pradesh were from the Telangana region (Kodandaram, 2009).

The erstwhile Andhra Pradesh government had various opportunities to transform the landscape of the Telangana region through lift irrigation, e.g., SLBC, SRBC, TGP⁹ and also a possible diversion through water lift at the Nagarjuna Sagar could have helped the districts of Nalgonda, Warangal, Karimnagar and Khammam districts of Telangana. There was an initiative to lift water from Godavari river through Dr BR Ambedkar Pranahita Chevella Sujala Sravanthi project around 2007 but could not see the light of the day due to inter-state issues with Maharashtra. This proposal, later, became the base for the Kaleshwaram project. It was revived only after state bifurcation. Hence, it was indeed a lost opportunity.

The lack of surface water supply and the increasing agricultural needs of the state caused extensive use of groundwater, leading to more outstanding depletion issues. Also, the hydrological regime in many regions (especially Nalgonda) is such that groundwater is not potable as it contains fluorine more than the permissible limits of 1 to 1.5 mg/litre (Simhadri, 1997). Considering these historical, socio-political, and economic issues, the Kaleshwaram multipurpose lift irrigation project, Mission Kakatiya¹⁰ and Mission Bhagiratha¹¹ made perfect sense to realise the vision for a 'golden Telangana'. The report shall investigate various stages of the Kaleshwaram Project in the next section.

5. Connecting dots through Kaleshwaram Project

Kaleshwaram¹², a village in Mahadevpur mandal in Jayashankar Bhupalpally district of Telangana (carved out from erstwhile Adilabad district), is the epicentre of this project.

Though the original idea, around 2007, was to divert 160 TMC of water by building a barrage at a place called Tummidihetti village (Kautala Mandal, Adilabad district) in the river Godavari basin, which would potentially irrigate 16.40 lakh acres in as many as seven districts of Telangana which include – Adilabad, Nizamabad, Karimnagar, Medak, Warangal, Nalgonda and Ranga Reddy, besides drinking water and water for industrial use. This was initially called Dr B.R. Ambedkar Pranahita-Chevella Sujala Sravanthi Project. Due to inter-state issues between the State of Maharashtra and erstwhile Andhra Pradesh, this could not take-off.

⁹ Srisailem Left Bank Canal (SLBC); Srisailem Right Branch Canal (SRBC) and Telugu Ganga Project (TGP).

¹⁰ Mission Kakatiya is to restore the minor irrigation sources aimed at retrieving the lost glory of minor irrigation in the state with community participation for ensuring sustainable water security.

¹¹ Mission Bhagiratha, launched in 216 to provide piped drinking water to every household in the state. The objective is to supply 60 TMC of water – 100 liters per capital per day.

¹² The village is named after a Hindu Temple known as KaleshwaraMukteswara Swamy Temple, which is significant because of the two Lingas found on a single pedestal – Lord Shiva and Lord Yama. The village is also a confluence point of the two rivers of Pranahitha and Godavari rivers.

Maharashtra wanted to bring down the proposed Full Reservoir Level (FRL) of +152 m to around 148m to avoid greater submergence in their territory due to the proposed FRL. Moreover, the Central Water Commission (CWC) also raised the need for more water availability and questioned the viability of the proposed project (Department of Irrigation, Government of Telangana, 2018)¹³. The proposal took a backseat for a few years until the new state of Telangana was formed and soon a re-engineering plan was initiated. The newly formed government in 2014 came with lot of energy and the desire to do something impactful and hence did not give up on the deadlocked proposal. Moreover, 'water for all' was one of the important agenda for the semi-arid Telangana.

Contemplating a new starting point in lieu of Tummidihetti, meant delaying the process by a couple of years. At this juncture, the latest technology came to rescue with WAPCOS (a mini-ratna under Ministry of Jal Shakti) by using LiDAR¹⁴ survey, saving lot of time. WAPCOS played an important role in the creation of Kaleshwaram project by identifying and proposing Medigadda village (near Kaleshwaram) in Mahadevpur mandal in erstwhile Karimnagar district (currently, it comes under Jayashankar Bhupalpally district) as the place to initiate the journey of Kaleshwaram Project. Various studies were quickly conducted and water availability was assessed as 284.3 TMC (against the proposed diversion of 191 TMC). The new location had two advantage: substantial reduction in the submergence area (to 285 acres) and, more water availability in Medigadda. It enhanced the scope to enlarge the project by combining and connecting two major projects into one – Dr BR Ambedkar Pranahita project (at Tummidihetti) to irrigate an ayacut of 2,00,000 acres as against the original proposed 56,500 acres in the east of Adilabad district and the proposed Kaleshwaram project starting from Medigadda.

Construction of a barrage across river Godavari at Medigadda near Kaleshwaram, and two more barrages between Medigadda and Sripada Yellampally Project at Annaram and Sundilla and to convey water from Sripada Yellampally Project to the command area spread over in 7 districts of Telangana (now 13 districts after re-organization of districts in the state) through components such as canals, tunnels, lift systems, reservoirs, and distribution network for irrigating an ayacut of 18,25,700 acres against the initially proposed ayacut of 16,40,000 acres.

Further, it is proposed to stabilise the existing ayacut in other major projects viz, Srisailem Sagar Reservoir (SRSP) – State-1, SRSP State-2, Flood Flow Canal, Singur & Nizamsagar projects to the extent of 18,82,970 acres. Besides irrigation, drinking water (30TMC for Hyderabad-Secunderabad and 10 TMC for en route villages) and water for industrial use (15 TMC) is also proposed.

¹³ The detailed water availability studies were carried out and assessed by the Central Water Commission, New Delhi. Accordingly, the net water availability at the barrage location (Tummidihetti) was assessed as about 165.38 TMC at 75% dependability which includes perceived surpluses of 63 TMC from the share of the states. Further, the CWC stated that availability of surpluses of 63 TMC from upstream states as estimated at the barrage site may not be reliably available in future. Even the Hydrology studies with FRL +152 m, the divertible water would be about 110 to 120 TMC against 160 TMC which was proposed and required.

¹⁴ LiDAR stands for Light Detection and Ranging.

Figure 1: Line Diagram of Kaleshwaram Project

Source: Department of Irrigation & CAD, Government of Telangana, 2021

Further, after careful planning, the proposed capacity of reservoirs is increased from 11.43 TMC to 147.71 TMC of water, stored collectively in 20 reservoirs in the uplands of as many as 13 districts. This was achieved by enhancing the capacities of existing reservoirs and proposing new reservoirs to match the demand and supply. The largest reservoir is the Sri Komaravally Mallana Sagar at Tadkapally which has a capacity of 50.00 TMC.

Table 1: Reservoirs under Kaleshwaram Project

S.No.	Name of the Reservoir	Original Capacity	Revised Capacity
1.	BARRAGE AT THUMMIDIHETTI		
	WITH FRL +152.00M	5	
	WITH FRL +148.00 M		1.85
2.	BARRAGE AT MEDIGADDA WITH FRL +100.00M		16.17
	BARRAGE AT ANNARAM FRL +119.0		10.87
	BARRAGE AT SUNDILLA FRL +130.0		8.83
3.	MEDARAM RESERVIOR	0.58	0.78
4.	MALKAPET RESERVOIR	0.35	3.00
5.	ANANTAGIRI RESERVOIR	1.7	3.50
6.	IMAMABAD RESERVOIR	1.5	3.00
7.	KOMARELLI MALLANNA SAGAR (TADKAPALLY)	1.5	50.00
8.	KONDAPOCHAMMA SAGAR RESERVOIR (PAMULAPARTHY)	1	15.00
9.	BASWAPUR RESERVOIR	0.8	11.39
10.	GANDHAMALLA RESERVOIR		9.87
11.	CHEVELLA RESERVOIR	3	-
12.	THIPPARAM RESERVOIR	1	
13.	KONDAMCHERUVU		3.50
14.	BHUMPALLY		0.09
15.	MOTHE RESERVOIR		1.50
16.	DHARMARAOPET		0.50
17.	KATEWADI		0.50
18.	DANTHEPALLI		0.50
19.	MUDDOJIWADI		0.50
20.	TIMMAKKAPALLY		1.50
21.	TOTAL	11.43	141.00

Source: Department of Irrigation & CAD, Government of Telangana, 2021

Table 2: Salient features of the Kaleshwaram Project

S.No.	Description	Particulars
1	Gravity Canal	1531 km
2	Tunnel	203 km
3	Pressure Mains / Delivery Mains	98 km
4	Total Length of the Water Conductor System	1832 km
5	No. of Lifts	20
6	No. of Reservoirs	20
7	Total Capacity of Reservoirs	147.71 TMC
8	Total Water being lifted from Godavari river	195 TMC
9	Water lifted from SYP	20 TMC
10	Ground Water	25 TMC
11	Total Water Availability	240 TMC
12	Water for Irrigation (New + Stabilization Ayacut)	169 TMC
13	Drinking Water Supply (Twin Cities & enroute villages)	40 TMC
14	Water supply to industries	16 TMC
15	Designed power rating	4627 MW
16	Districts benefitted (New Ayacut)	13 Districts
17	Total Districts covered in New / Stabilization Ayacut	20 Districts

Source: Department of Irrigation & CAD, Government of Telangana, 2022

The project is divided into seven links. Each link conveys the water from a source to a storage system and/or distributary network system to irrigate the ayacut. Some interesting facts about the project are:

- ▶ It consumed more than 30 times the concrete than the Burj Khalifa in Dubai
- ▶ It involved more than 75 times more earthwork than Hoover Dam, Nevada.

Table 3: Links and its Command Area

Link No.	Particulars	Command Area	
		Hectares	Acres
Link-1	From Medigadda Barrage on Godavari River to Sripada Yellapally Project	12141	30000
Link-2	From Sripada Yellampally Project to Mid Manair Reservoir (Package 6,7&8)	-	-
Link-3	From Mid Manair Reservoir to Upper Manair Reservoir (Package 9)	34864	86150
Link-4	From Mid Manair Reservoir to Konda Pochamma Reservoir (Package 10,11,12,13 & 14)	238478	589280
Link-5	From Anicut to Chityala (Package 15 & 16)	101902	251800
Link-6	From Sri Komaravelly Mallana Sagar to Singur Reservoir (Package 17,18,19)	133161	329042
Link-7	From SRSP Foreshore to Nizam Sagar Canals and upto Kondem Cheruvu (Package 20,21 & 22) and to Dilwapur (Package 27) and Hangarga (Package 28) village for Nirmal and Mudhole Constituency	218304	539428
TOTAL		738851	182570

Source: Department of Irrigation & CAD, Government of Telangana, 2022

The Kaleshwaram Project stands as the world's largest lift irrigation project with three barrages, 1531 km of gravity canals, 203 km of tunnels, 20 lifts, 19 pump houses and 20 reservoirs, with a total capacity of 195 TMC water irrigating around 37 lakh acres.

5.1 Uniqueness of Kaleshwaram Project

Kaleshwaram project is unique on multiple fronts.

Speedy Implementation: India's multipurpose larger irrigation projects took decades to complete. For example, the Indira Sagar Project in Madhya Pradesh started in 1984 and was completed twenty-one years later in 2005. The Sardar Sarovar Project in Gujrat started in 1980 and could only be commissioned in 2017 (delayed due to the strong Narmada Bachao Movement). Perhaps the governance model, quick leadership decisions, and use of the latest technologies helped complete the project within three years of laying the foundation stone.

Statutory Clearances: Getting statutory clearances for such large projects often takes years, as multiple departments must use their expert knowledge and offer formal approval. Some of the major ones were – the Department of Hydrology, Inter-State Matters (ISM), Construction Machinery Consultancy (CMC), Irrigation Planning, Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare, Cost Appraisal Committee, Central Soil & Materials Research Station (CSMRS), Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change, Central Groundwater Board (CGWB), National Board for Wildlife, Technical Advisory Committee (TAC), besides others. Meticulous follow-up by the Irrigation Department officials with the multiple regulators helped to get timely clearances.

Institutional Associations: Many institutes and government/private agencies, both central and state, conducted various studies to make things happen. Some of them were – the Central Design Organization, Central Board of Irrigation and Power (CBIP), WAPCOS, Telangana State Engineering Research Labs (TSERL), Engineering Materials Laboratory (TSEER), Indian Institute of Science (IISc), VASSAR Labs IT Solutions Pvt. Ltd., National Institute of Rock Mechanics (NIRM), KPMG, besides others. Their contribution was indeed the backbone for the entire project, which gave the required scientific backup to the envisioned engineering marvel.

Funding the project: A project of such a magnitude often comes with a considerable budget. The actual cost of the project worked out to Rs.80190.46 crores which was approved by the Central Water Commission (CWC) and the Technical Advisory Committee (TAC). As the need for a newly formed state government will have multiple areas to spend, it would not have been able to directly invest around 1 lakh crores on a single project. Typically, for such large projects, a Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV) is formed, which raises the required monetary resources through banks and financial institutions. They raise funds by collateralizing future receivables. The funding from international agencies (like WB, ABD, etc.) could have been a problem as they often insist on a cost-benefit analysis report with a minimum EIRR between 10 to 13%. The project was not eligible for a national project status, as it had no investment clearance from the Centre (Apparasu, 2022). Moreover, since 13th Finance Commission recommendations, there has been a policy directive to reduce the number of Centrally Sponsored Schemes (CSS) and to restore the predominance of formula-based plan transfers (Thirteenth Finance Commission, 2009). The most plausible way to execute such a project was to form a special purpose vehicle and raise the required money through various financial institutions and banks. Hence Kaleshwaram Irrigation Project Corporation Limited (KIPCL) came into force on 5th August 2016. Though the Corporation was successful in raising the required monetary resources for the project, and it is 80% complete, the corporation is paying heavy interest on the loans taken.

The Government also decided to supplement the budgetary resources with extra resources to fasten development. According to the Telangana's Socio-Economic Outlook (2022), from 2014-15 to 2021-22 (till 31.1.2022), apart from the expenditure incurred from the budget (Rs. 1.67 lakh crores), Rs. 1.14 lakh crores were spent for capital expenditure, leading to a total capital expenditure of nearly Rs. 2.82 lakh crores, which is more than 5 times the capital expenditure incurred in the 10 years before the bifurcation of the state. Such an increased capital expenditure is unprecedented. From this it is pretty clear that most of the non-plan expenditure went to sponsor Kaleshwaram project. Annexure-II details the Statutory Clearances for Kaleshwaram Project.

Land Acquisition: One more critical aspect is land acquisition, which indeed is an important achievement in a very short period. Though land acquisition was not a major issue around the Medigadda area because of the topography, it was indeed a major task in the uplands where the reservoirs were planned, and land had to be submerged – Ranganayaka Sagar, Komaravelly

Mallanna Sagar, Konda Pochamma, Gandamalla, Basawapoor and Anantagiri reservoirs, mostly in and around Siddipet district. It was observed that 40% of the total land requirement for the project needed displacement of the villagers. It was reported that 20,878 persons (8,300 project-displaced families) had to be displaced to acquire 35,000 acres of land. It is indeed a record that 95% of land acquisition was completed between 2018-2020.

5.2 Impact of KLIP on Development

One of the major purposes of the project is to provide irrigation to the upland districts of Telangana and reduce the dependence on depleting groundwater for agriculture. The combination of Kaleshwaram Project and Mission Kakatiya (reclamation of tanks by restoring the minor irrigation sources) has the potential to solve most of the water requirements for the State's agriculture. Also, through this project, the industrial sector can be provided with 16 TMC of water. These aspects could be seen as investments to improve the agricultural productivity of the State as well as help industrialization. The project also helps in supplying drinking water to areas of water scarcity in the State, especially Hyderabad. This is linked to the mission to provide piped drinking water to every household in the State, called Mission Bhagiratha. It is strongly believed that the access to drinking water will help improve the quality of life and strengthen overall productivity.

Impact on Agriculture: Three years down, the benefits of the project are already visible. Even though only about 17 lakh acres of irrigated land has been added as of now, the state has witnessed a 42% rise in agricultural production in 2020-21. The paddy cultivation is expected to increase from about 40 to 70 lakh acres, making Telangana the country's rice bowl. Currently, Telangana is facing the problem of plenty of paddy production, partly due to the Kaleshwaram Project and excess due to excess rainfall in the past two years, triggered probably by a year of total lockdown due to the pandemic impacting the environment positively.

Department of Irrigation & CAD, Government of Telangana also conducted crop impact analysis in Kaleshwaram (Link-4) for two crop seasons (Vanakalam, i.e. Khariff) and Yasangi, i.e., Rabi) for four years between 2018-19 and 2021-22. It is found that the command areas of Annapurna Reservoir, Ranganayaka Sagar Reservoir, and Mallanna Sagar Reservoir have shown improved land fertility as it was converted from dry or fallow land to wetland. Annexure III has more details on the impact of Kaleshwaram on crop production.

Recharging water beds: The water flowing through these systems will meet the agricultural, drinking and industrial needs and recharge the water beds and reduce environmental loads in perennially water-starved catchments.

Impact on Tourism: The KLIP also created new avenues for tourism as the new reservoirs started attracting the general public. The Rangnayak Sagar, the Konda Pochamma, Mallana Sagar, among others, have developed immense scope for tourism.

Fisheries development: The huge amount of artificial water bodies upstream created due to the project also enables the development of fisheries as a livelihood option for many of the farmers in the command area.

Table 4: EPTRI analysis on benefits without and with the project

Item	Without Project	With Project
Cropped area	2,85,530 ha	9,61,498 ha
Net value of produce	Rs. 5432.139 million	Rs. 161384.160 million
Drinking Water supply		Rs. 16988.40 million
Industrial Water supply		Rs. 40772.16 million
Fisheries*		Rs. 1500.00 million
TOTAL		Rs. 215212.581 million

*Average reservoir area x Rate as per Fisheries Dept

Source: Environmental Protection Training and Research Institute (EPTRI), 2016

Overall, the impact of the project is positive on the development of the State, though the cost of building the project is on the higher side for a state government. The project also strengthened India's positioning as it is now capable of matching the best in the world in terms of the timely execution of complex engineering projects.

6. How sustainable is Kaleshwaram Project for the State of Telangana?

One important enquiry that needs to be analyzed is the correlation between sustainable development and the Kaleshwaram Project for the State of Telangana, which calls for a deeper analysis into the aspects of – environmental clearance, land acquisition and financing.

Large infrastructure projects involving water resources inevitably highlight trade-offs between environment and development, as well as challenges along both fronts simultaneously. Telangana's semi-arid zone of the Deccan plateau, covering as many as 13 districts (out of the total 33 districts), needed developmental attention as they are drought-prone, have lesser economic opportunities and are relatively poverty ridden. Development is usually generous to the people around the rivers, which can only help improve the state's growth rate but not the region's overall development. Drought¹⁵ is

¹⁵ The Irrigation Commission (1972) defined 'drought' as a situation occurring in an area where the annual rainfall is less than 75% of the normal in 20% of the years examined.

probably the worst form of natural disaster that humanity has ever confronted. For a farmer, drought means a moisture availability shortage in the crop's root zone. Drought brings misery to human life, creating a shortage of soil moisture in agricultural lands and drinking water for human beings and cattle. The incidences of famine in world history are almost always a consequence of droughts.

About one-sixth of the area of India is drought-prone. Recurrent droughts have greatly deter the economic development of over one-third of the area. Nearly 30% of India's population is affected by drought, of which Telangana is one (Simhadri, 1997).

The National Water Policy (NWP) of India, adopted in 1987, revised in 2002, and further revised in 2012, recommended combating drought-associated problems through soil-moisture conservation measures, water harvesting practices, minimization of evaporation losses, development of the groundwater potential and transfer of surplus water from surplus areas, where feasible and appropriate, to deficit ones. In planning water resources development projects, the needs of the drought-prone areas should be given priority (Michael, 2008p. 107).

The Kaleshwaram lift irrigation project, which is about lifting Godavari river around 610 meters above msl to bring water to as many as 13 districts of semi-arid landscapes, benefiting 18.25 lakh acres of rainfed land cultivated by small and marginal farmers, involves some of these trade-offs. The main negative trade-offs between the environment and development involved in this project are - land acquisition due to submergence and forest land occupied for the project. The total forest land displaced was 3,168.1315 Ha (0.125% of Telangana's total forest land of 25,40,000 ha), most of it in the districts of Siddipet, Jayashankar Bhoopalpally, Sirchilla, Nizamabad and Nirmal. The forest land was taken to build gravity canals and for submergence purposes¹⁶.

6.1 Environmental Clearance

There are multiple aspects involved in getting environmental clearance for such a gigantic project. On behalf of the Irrigation Department, EHSCPL- Bengaluru (2018) conducted an environmental impact assessment study for the purpose of getting clearance from MoEF&CC, Govt. of India. Many standard environmental attributes were taken into consideration (both at the construction and operation phase, respectively) and the nature of impacts (magnitude, reversible, irreversible, long term, short term, direct, indirect, positive, and negative) was analyzed. It was observed that the impact on most of the environmental attributes showed either a major or significant impact on most of the parameters, which calls for an Environment Management Plan (EMP). Without investing in EMP, the project could not be declared viable. The environment clearance was granted by the Environment Ministry on February 25, 2020, subject to adherence to EMP. The Irrigation department allocated a budget of around Rs.138 crores (precisely Rs.1,37,72,30,770/-, which is around 0.12% of the total project

¹⁶ It is a requirement that when forest land is taken for any public purpose, it is the responsibility of the department to conduct a Compensatory Afforestation (CA). The Irrigation department mutated the CA lands in favour of the Forest department.

budget) to implement EMP (70% during the construction phase and 30% during the operation phase) in Mahadevpur mandal.

Even after EMP, the management of musk created from the project potentially negatively impacted the environment. In this regard, the Government submitted a detailed Musk Disposal Plan to the regulators. The quantity of musk generated from various project activities like earthwork and excavation for the foundation is 1,16,673 cum. One innovative management of the generated musk could be seen in this project. The musk generated is completely reused for embankment, filling trenches, land levelling service paths etc.

In addition to EMP and musk management, it was required to look at the impact on flora and fauna for environmental clearance. As required, biodiversity assessment was carried on around Mahadevpur Mandal and it was found that the mega faunal species, such as sloth bear, wild boar, fox, barasingha, nilgai, sambar deer, jungle cats etc. are the commonly recorded species in the study area due to the presence of Mahadevpur Reserved Forest nearby. As per IUCN Conservation status, 2017 two vulnerable species namely, sambar deer and sloth bear were recorded. Of which, Sloth bear and Sambar Deer belongs to Schedule-I and Schedule-III of Wildlife (Protection) Act, 1972 respectively. However, no such mega faunal species were recorded during the study. Totally 105 fish species were recorded in Godavari river and the Fisheries Department studied the environmental factors and zoogeographical distribution pattern of each fish variety¹⁹.

Due to the project's possible impact on the fish fauna, attention is to be diverted towards the development of large-sized indigenous fish species like sportfish and cold-water fish. As per the baseline survey conducted by the Forest Department, Black kite, Black shouldered kite, Oriental honey buzzard (birds), common Pierrot (butterfly) and sloth bear (mammal) are the schedule-I species recorded. A wildlife conservation and management plan for Schedule-I species was submitted to the Environment Ministry for the environmental clearance for the project. Overall, most of the environmental attributes were taken care of by supplementing the efforts through environmental management plans at various levels.

¹⁷ Attributes during the Construction Phase include - Air pollution (increase in dust concentration, fugitive emissions, increase in SO₂, PM & NO_x), noise pollution (movement of vehicles and operation of DG sets), water pollution (Eutrophication, change in river water quality, change in groundwater quality, impact on human health), land pollution (change in topography, productive soil, compaction soil, contamination of soil, solid and hazardous waste), soil pollution, biological environment (pressure on existing natural resources, reduced photosynthetic activity, wilting of plants, impacts on fishes and aquatic ecosystem, impact on schedule-1 species, near-by agro-ecosystems), impacts on hydrology and geology (geological environment, seismic tectonics, hydraulic regime), impact on the socio-economic environment (land acquisition and impact on human health. Attributes during the Operation Phase include – the application of natural fertilizers and pesticides, salinity of irrigated land, groundwater recharge, local biodiversity, employment, impact on the water environment, impact on aquatic life, and impact due to project failure.

¹⁸ It was also mentioned in the Environmental Clearance approval that the project should require at least 1.5% investment (i.e., Rs.1,205 crores) to the total project capital investment (Rs.80,321.57 crores) through Corporate Environment Responsibility (CER) by the industry. However, the project proposal and approval were for Kannepally Village, Mahadevpur Mandal, Jayshankar Bhoopalpally District, Telangana and not for the entire stretch of the impact area of around 13 districts.

¹⁹ The distance from the project site (and pump house) to the Siwaram Wildlife Sanctuary boundary (16.832 kms.) and the Pranahita Wildlife Sanctuary boundary (12 kms.), including the Eco-Sensitive Zones of both these Sanctuaries (15.74kms and 7kms, respectively), is considered to be as per the norms.

6.2 Land Acquisition for Kaleshwaram

A sustainable development plan also takes into consideration socio-economic factors, especially the displacement and rehabilitation process due to land acquisition for project purposes need detailed analysis. Land acquisition was not a major issue in the parts where Barrages and Lift systems were built, i.e., Karimnagar and Jayashankar Bhoopalpally districts, as most of it was close to the riverbed and part of forest land. However, it was a major issue of concern in the places of water storage, mostly in the district of Siddipet situated at an average elevation of +610m above msl, where large reservoirs were created (Annapurna Reservoir, Sri Ranganayaka Sagar Reservoir, Sri Komaravelli Mallana Sagar Reservoir, and Kondapochamma Sagar Reservoir). The combined holding capacity of these four reservoirs is 71.5 TMC with four pump houses, which is to serve (new ayacut) 3.3 lakh acres along with stabilization ayacut of about 40,000 acres across 19 mandals and 284 villages. There is a need to understand the background of Land Acquisition in India and Telangana, before we get into details of Land Acquisition for Kaleshwaram.

Land Acquisition Act of 1894 was replaced by Right to Fair Compensation and Transparency in Land Acquisition Rehabilitation and Resettlement Act, 2013. Few essential aspects were added to this Act to actualize land acquisition by the Government. They are – clause on compensation, rehabilitation and resettlement, and social impact assessment survey²⁰. As land acquisition is an essential aspect of infrastructure development, the governance systems wanted to ensure that the laws don't come on the way. At the same time, it should address the critical aspects of land acquisition. With the change in the government at the Centre in 2014, the new government introduced an Amendment to the 2013 Act and introduced The Right to Fair Compensation and Transparency in Land Acquisition, Rehabilitation and Resettlement (Amendment) Bill 2015, which was passed in the Lok Sabha as an Ordinance, but Rajya Sabha referred it to a Joint Parliamentary Committee (JPC), and hence could not see the light of the day. The issue of the threshold for consent from landowners became an unresolved issue. A comparison of the proposed 2015 bill as against the 2013 Act is given in ANNEXURE – 1.

The Bill enables the government to exempt five categories of projects from the requirements of: (i) SIA, (ii) restrictions on acquisition of multi-cropped land, and (iii) consent for PPPs and private projects. These five categories of projects are: (i) defence, (ii) rural infrastructure, (iii) affordable housing, (iv) industrial corridors, and (v) infrastructure including PPPs where the government owns the land²¹. These five exempted categories may cover many types of projects for which land may be acquired. A table below (compiled by PRS) compares 'public purpose' projects for which land may be acquired under the 2013 Act with the types of projects that may be exempted from the three conditions stated above by the Bill (PRS India, n.d.).

²⁰ However, one of the key issues is that the requirement of a Social Impact Assessment for every acquisition without a minimum threshold may delay the implementation of certain government programmes.

²¹ However, terms such as - rural infrastructure, affordable housing, and industrial corridors, are not defined in the 2013 Act or the 2015 Bill and may be open to interpretation.

Table 5: Land Acquisition 2013 Act and 2015 Bill

Projects for which land can be acquired under the 2013 Act	Projects exempt under the 2015 Bill	Projects for which requirements under 2013 Act will apply
Strategic purposes relating to the armed forces, or any work vital to national security, defence of India, or state police	Projects vital to national security or defence of India including preparation for defence or defence production	Projects related to state police
Infrastructure projects, relating to agro-processing, water harvesting, industrial corridors, government schemes, etc*	Infrastructure projects including those under PPPs where the ownership of land vests with the government. Industrial corridors set-up by the government and its undertakings (in which case the land acquired shall be up to one kilometer on both sides of the designated railway line or roads). Rural infrastructure including electrification	Industrial corridors for any land acquired beyond one kilometre of designated railway line or roads
Planned development of village sites or any site in the urban areas	Infrastructure projects including projects under PPPs where the ownership of land continues to vest with the government. Rural infrastructure including electrification	Items that do not fall under infrastructure i.e. private hospitals, private educational institutions and private hotels.
Project for project affected families	Affordable housing and housing for poor people	Any project for project affected families other than affordable housing and housing for poor people
Housing of income groups, as specified by the government	Affordable housing and housing for poor people	Housing which is (i) not affordable housing and (ii) for income groups not specified by the government
Residential purposes to the poor or landless	Affordable housing and housing for poor people	None

Sources: Right to Fair Compensation and Transparency in Land Acquisition, Rehabilitation and Resettlement Act, 2013; Right to Fair Compensation and Transparency in Land Acquisition, Rehabilitation and Resettlement (Second Amendment) Bill, 2015; PRS.

*Note: *Involves projects which: (a) are listed in a notification (No. 13/6/2009-INF) by the Department of Economic Affairs, (such as infrastructure related to transport, energy, water and sanitation, communication, social and commercial infrastructure including cold chains, fertiliser, post-harvest infrastructure, common infrastructure for industrial parks and SEZs etc.) but excluding private hospitals, educational institutions and hotels (b) involve agro-processing, agricultural inputs, (c) for industrial corridors and National Investment and Management Zones, (d) for water harvesting, (e) for government aided or administered educational schemes, (f) for sports facilities, and (g) any other infrastructure facility notified by the central government.*

Though the land is a state subject, many aspects of it are in a concurrent list, including land acquisition. This makes the Right to Fair Compensation and Transparency in Land Acquisition, Rehabilitation and Resettlement Act (LARR) the principal legal document on land acquisition, and the State Governments base their land legislation on this. A close examination of Telangana's amendments to the principal document gives a sense that many of the amendments were carried to facilitate Kaleshwaram Project. The Right to Fair Compensation and Transparency in Land Acquisition, Rehabilitation and Resettlement (Telangana Amendment) Act, 2016, Act 21 of 2017 became the primary document for Telangana's land acquisition for public purpose. The State of Telangana used its power to exempt certain projects to facilitate Kaleshwaram (Chapter-III A, which was inserted from the principal document, talked about certain exemptions. "Provisions of Chapter-II and III not to apply to certain projects", which also includes – infrastructure including electrification and irrigation projects {10A (b)} (PRS India, n.d.). Also, the amendment gives space to the Government to enter into an agreement with the land owners (Voluntary Acquisition of Land under Chapter IV-A of the Act²²). In order to give priority to the public purpose projects, Government of Telangana, earlier on July 30, 2015, issued a Government Order 123 (G.O.MS.No. 123), which gave the Collector a free hand to negotiate outside the purview of the principal central Govt. Act of LARR 2013.

The GO says:

In order to expeditiously procure land for public projects, Government deem it fit to come out with a framework that allows the landowners to participate in the development process by willingly sell their land and properties thereon, for a consideration on the basis of an agreement between land owners and the user department/undertaking/society/authority, herein-after called as Procuring Agency, as approved by the District Level Land Procurement Committee (DLLPC)

cit. G.O. MS. No. 123 dated 30.07.2015 Revenue (JA&LA) Department, Government of Telangana.

²² 30A: (1) Notwithstanding anything contained in the Principal Act, or any other law, whenever it appears to the State Government that the land is needed in any area for any public purpose, the State Government or its authorized officer will enter into an agreement with the willing land owner to sell the land in favour of the State for the matters specified therein in a prescribed form.....(4) If any family, other than the family of the land owners who entered into an agreement, is affected by the acquisition of land under this section, the State Government shall pay a lumpsum amount towards rehabilitation and resettlement, if any, as prescribed in the rules hereunder: Provided that no agreement or the lumpsum amount towards rehabilitation and resettlement as may be prescribed, shall be abnormally at variance to the disadvantage of the land owners". For more see https://prsindia.org/files/bills_acts/acts_states/telangana/2017/2017Telangana21.pdf accessed on 28-10-2022

The GO provided flexibility to landowners on rehabilitation and resettlement (R&R) where the displaced persons could choose money in place of R&R. However, the issue was with the people/farmers who depended on that land, not necessarily as landowners. This issue made the High Court give a decision against the GO123 on January 04, 2017 and declared that the state shall henceforth not purchase lands under Government Order Ms No. 123 dated July 30, 2015, for the public purpose of construction of irrigation projects. But it carried on with the process of land acquisition for public purposes through LARR (Telangana Amendment) Act 2017, which also offered a free hand to the Collector, though in a more structured way.

To actualize the Kaleshwaram project, there was a need to acquire 86,110 acres which has a trade-off for as many as 20,878 families needing resettlement and rehabilitation²³. This land was required primarily for submergence purposes giving way to creation of Konda Pochamma Sagar Reservoir, Sri Komaravelli Mallanna Sagar Reservoir and the Ananthagiri Reservoir. One of the important reasons for the success of the kaleshwaram project was to acquire this part of the land with consent and make it uninhabitable. The polity and the legal systems helped prioritize the Kaleshwaram project and facilitated the compromise through resettlement, compensation and skill development. It was, to an extent a good trade-off, but it was also important for the PDFs to make the best use of the compensation they received. An advisory on how best they could make use of the compensation amount for long-term sustainable benefits as well as short-term issues, would have been helpful for those unfortunate families. Also, the global COVID-19 Pandemic came at a very unfortunate time for them, increasing their worries about unemployment and joblessness.

40% of the land acquisition for the Kaleshwaram project happened in the Siddipet districts to acquire around 35,000 acres. Out of the total land required for four reservoirs along with canal systems and distributary network systems in Siddipet District, almost 95% of the land was acquired in a record time of 18 months duration between 2018 to 2020. Around 28,000 families were affected due to land acquisition. Almost 99% of the land acquired under this district is with “Consent” without any force or litigation/court case with the stakeholders.

It was important to think about the long-term impact of the displaced. When they are no more landowners, their livelihoods often become a question mark. The displaced must be offered skills required for the future. Hence, the district administration facilitated Skill development through industry partnership by involving TATA Strive, which provided training for about 600 local apprentices and have provided employment for them in TATA group of companies. Though the State Government met its commitments for procuring the required land for Kaleshwaram project with due compensation, and also created some of the largest R&R colonies; the livelihood issues still needed to be resolved. One of the primary reasons being the advent of the Covid-19 pandemic leading to a slowdown in the economy and, subsequently, lesser demand for job-work.

²³ The number of PDFs (People of Displace Families) could be more as the land acquisition process is still on. As on January 20, 2022, the balance of land to be acquired still was 24,208 acres.

6.3 Financing Kaleshwaram

According to Telangana's Socio-Economic Survey 2022, Telangana's share of development expenditure in the total expenditure in the 2017-20 period was 77.4%, which happened to be the highest among the general states (GS). Telangana stands second among GS regarding the average per capita development expenditure incurred during the 2017-20 period. In order to execute a gigantic project like Kaleshwaram, which is expected to help in the process of accelerated development of the state, the planned and budgetary expenditure wouldn't have been sufficient. From 2014-15 to 2021-22, the expenditure incurred from the budget was 1.67 lakh crores and hence an additional 1.14 lakh crores were spent for capital expenditure. The Government also decided to supplement the budgetary resources with extra budgetary resources to accommodate large irrigation projects like Kaleshwaram and Bhagiratha. From 2014-15 to 2021-22, Rs. 1.14 lakh crores were spent for capital expenditure, leading to a total capital expenditure of nearly Rs. 2.82 lakh crores. Such an increase in capital expenditure is unprecedented (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2022).

The total cost of the Kaleshwaram Project approved by the Central Water Commission (CWC) is Rs.80,190.46 crores, which was to be expended through a Special Purpose Vehicle – Kaleshwaram Irrigation Project Corporation Limited (KIPCL). It came into existence from August 2016. The Corporation is involved in developing, engineering, financing and executing the Kaleshwaram Project. The corporation tied up with a consortium of banks and other financial institutions to raise the required funds²⁴. The corporation also has the mandate to include Palamuru Rangareddy Lift Irrigation Scheme (PRLIS).

²⁴ KIPCL is classified as State Government company and is registered at the Registrar of Companies, Hyderabad. Its authorized share capital is 100 crores and its paid-up capital is 100 crores.

Table 6: Breakup of the approved cost of Rs.80,190.46 crores

S. No.	Name of Item	Amount (Rs. in crores)
1	Works	63352.00
2	Sub-Stations	2885.84
3	Land	6953.65
4	Resettlement & Rehabilitation	1464.34
5	Forest Land	741.52
6	Operations & Maintenance	661.08
7	Establishment charges @2%	1365.43
8	Tools & Plants and Recoveries	769.27
9	Miscellaneous	868.51
Total Direct Charges (1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9)		79061.64
10	Indirect charges (Capital value of land abatement)	359.55
11	Audit & Account charges	769.27
Total Indirect Charges (10+11)		1128.82
GRAND TOTAL		80190.46

Source: <http://www.irrigation.telangana.gov.in/img/projectspdf/kaleshwaram.pdf> accessed on 29.10.2022

The Aggregate borrowing limit of KIPCL is Rs. 1,31,280 Cr. The total borrowings sanctioned so far are:

- ▶ For Kaleshwaram Project – Rs. 86,064.01 Cr Including IDC & Rs. 74,843.80 Cr Excluding IDC.
- ▶ For Palamuru Rangareddy Lift Irrigation Scheme – Rs. 10,000 Cr including IDC & Rs. 7660.46 Cr excluding IDC.
- ▶ Thus, the total sanctioned financial assistance to KIPCL so far amounts to Rs. 96,064.01 Cr. (incl IDC) and Rs. 82,504.26 Cr (excluding IDC).
- ▶ Total amount released so far is Rs. 57,216.41 Cr against a sanctioned loan of Rs. 82,504.26 Cr.

Source: Department of Irrigation & CAD, Govt. of Telangana, 2022

It is useful to make a note on how the State Government raised the required amount. It took loans from multiple banks and financing agencies, through KIPCL.

Table 7: Loans taken for Kaleshwaram Project by KIPCL

S.No.	Name of the Lender	Amount Sanctioned	Rate of Interest
1	Andhra Bank Consortium	7400.00	8.25%
2	PNB Consortium	11400.00	8.25%
3	Vijaya Bank	2150.00	8.25%
4	PFC Loan 88603001	12067.36	9.80%
5	PFC Loan 886030A1	2379.56	9.80%
6	PFC Loan 886030B1	5405.39	10.76%
7	PFC Loan 886030C1	4075.11	11.00%
8	PFC Loan 886030D1	2424.54	11.00%
9	NABARD Loan -I	1500.00	9.75%
10	NABARD Loan-II	4674.83	7.80%
11	NABARD Loan-III	2051.14	7.80%
12	REC Loan for Link -I	4657.95	10.90%
13	REC Loan for Link -II	11784.70	10.90%
14	REC Loan for Link -IV	14093.43	10.90%

Source: Department of Irrigation and CAD, Government of Telangana, 2022

Note: Amount in Crores

All these loans ought to be cleared by the State Government by the end of year 2034. The annual cost, according to the DPR, including interest, electricity cost, and annual maintenance charges, will be Rs 13,923 crore. This includes interest, electricity costs, annual maintenance charges, depreciation of the equipment etc. It would mean that the government needs to spend 53,000 per acre every year towards O&M (Ishaqui , 2017). With the speed at which this project took off, there was no issues of cost escalation, which normally happens with most of the large-scale irrigation and infrastructure projects.

Table 8: Budget and Expenditure for Kaleshwaram Project (in Rs. crores)

Financial Year	Budget Allotted	Govt. Expenditure Incurred	Expenditure through KIPCL from Banks & Fis	Total since Inception
2007-08	--	--	--	--
2008-09	260.00	176.66	--	176.66
2009-10	600.00	602.65	--	602.65
2010-11	700.00	64.02	--	64.02
2011-12	608.29	511.00	--	511.00
2012-13	1050.00	1851.17	--	1851.17
2013-14	782.06	2093.00	--	2093.00
2014-15	2018.35	1913.27	--	1913.27
2015-16	1769.13	2934.87	--	2934.87
2016-17	6286.00	4940.52	491.88	5432.40
2017-18	6691.87	1622.34	12417.14	14039.51
2018-19	6104.41	541.87	17328.53	17870.40
2019-20	2428.56	2286.80	9121.99	11408.79
2020-21	6025.02	3924.33	7376.87	11301.20
2021-22	7921.50	1736.73	8385.91	10122.64
Total	43245.19	25199.25	55122.32	80321.57

Source: Department of Irrigation & CAD, Government of Telangana, 2022

There has been criticism concerning Kaleshwaram project, especially about the amount of money being diverted towards making this project successful. The best way to look into this aspect is to see the immediate positive impact, though the project must be seen as a long-term developmental initiative. The immediate impact on the agriculture sector showed positive results when the Irrigation Department conducted a crop impact analysis in Kaleshwaram link-4 (refer Table-3 for Link details). An analysis of crop patter by the Agriculture Department of Govt of Telangana indicated that during the pre-project period, farmers used 40% of land to produce paddy, but the yield and net income was almost 500% lesser than what they are getting post-project. Also in the post-project period, farmers could diversify their product base, even during Kharif season due to access to quality water, by including cotton, ground nut, pigeon pea, chillies, soya bean, turmeric and vegetables²⁵. More importantly, there is a substantial increase in the yield and income that the farmers are expected to receive due to the Kalehwaram project. Below two tables give a comparative picture of certain crop patterns in pre-project and post-project period in the Kharif season.

²⁵ Paddy procurement could be one of the issues for product diversification during the Kharif season.

Table 9: Crop Pattern and Productivity Pre-Project/Pre-ERM

S.No.	Crop (Kharif)	Area	Total Yield	Gross Income	Total Expenditure	Net Income
1	Paddy	112395	1123950	19107.15	8362.19	10744.96
2	Cotton	6838	102570	3897.66	537.4	3360.26
3	Pigeon Pea	24694	222246	8889.84	1007.52	7882.32
4	Groundnut	3965	59475	2396.84	279.18	2117.66
5	Chillies	2370	35550	3910.5	310.38	3600.12
6	Soyabean	25650	461700	13851	1343.03	12507.97
7	Turmeric	6846	109536	3833.76	40963	2804.33
8	Vegetables	3679	73580	1471.6	33628	1237.17
TOTAL (includes other crops)		285530	3277625	71359.2	17087.56	54271.68

Source: Department of Agriculture, Govt. of Telangana, 2022

Table 10: Proposed Crop Pattern and Productivity Post-Project

(All rates in Rs.; Amount in Rs. Lakh and Area in Ha)

S.No.	Crop (Kharif)	Area	Total Yield	Gross Income	Total Expenditure	Net Income
1	Paddy	111323	5566150	94625	8436	86189
2	Cotton	111323	3896305	148060	9515	138545
3	Pigeon Pea	20038	440836	17633	942	16691
4	Groundnut	100191	4007640	161508	7054	154454
5	Chillies	100191	3005730	330630	15292	315338
6	Soyabean	111323	4452920	133588	6755	126833
7	Turmeric	95404	4006968	140244	19024	121220
8	Vegetables	89058	5343480	106870	8410	98460
TOTAL (includes other crops)		738851	30720029	1133158	75428	1057730

Source: Department of Agriculture, Govt. of Telangana, 2022

7. Concluding Observations

Kaleshwaram Lift Irrigation Project is visualized big to address the region's long-pending developmental issues. Its topography demanded the lifting of the river to meet the water requirements of the semi-arid uplands of Telangana for as many as 13 districts. Technology and the political will of the new State helped ideate and commission such an engineering marvel. To carry on with records, this was taken up at lightning speed, and 80% of the work was completed within three years from its inception and became the world's largest lift irrigation project. With a 1.55 benefit-to-cost ratio, it is worth an investment for a newly carved state. With this project, Telangana has laid the seeds to meet the state's long-term developmental objectives.

With the Kaleshwaram project, along with Mission Kakatiya (minor irrigation through tanks) and Mission Bhagiratha (piped drinking water to all), Telangana cemented its base for accelerating development. As most of the economic progress, historically, happened around the river streams, and in contrast, poverty is reported more in the upstream regions, it is bound to create inequality in the society, as it is observed that more concentration of SC/ST and OBC populations away from the main river streams. When Kaleshwaram Project starts giving results, it is expected to reduce inequalities in societies by giving more economic opportunities to the upstream populations.

Kaleshwaram can be seen as an integrated water management model in Telangana, envisioned by value addition to the existing water networks, reviving neglected tank systems (minor irrigation) by lifting the Godavari River wherever required at multiple levels. It is envisioned as a long-term project with future positive implications. As of date, we need to wait to see the true impact of Kaleshwaram, though some impacts could be seen almost instantly, like an increase in paddy production, improvement in groundwater, escalation of real-estate prices, development of tourism around reservoirs, besides others. Land acquisition is a trade-off, as there will be some losers. Farmers will prefer land over money at any given point, as many of them expressed when the ISB team conducted multiple focus group discussions and key informant interviews. But they needed to have a choice, and also that the government had offered the best way out with competitive compensation with fast delivery.

Now that we have Kaleshwaram up and running, it is important to address some of the future concerns, which are outlined as below:

1. Behavioural change amongst farmers

The need for behavioural change among farmers regarding their obsession with paddy cultivation and educating them about market vulnerabilities is crucial for sustainable agriculture and rural development. Farmers in regions like Telangana, with a semi-arid landscape and heavy reliance on rainwater and groundwater for agriculture, must diversify their crops and adapt to market demands for economic stability and reduced environmental impact. Paddy cultivation requires a significant

amount of water, putting pressure on already scarce resources. Moreover, the market for paddy can be volatile, with fluctuating prices and uncertain demand. Farmers who solely focus on paddy may face financial hardships if they are not prepared to adjust to changing market conditions.

To address this, farmers need to be educated about alternative crops suitable for their region and with higher market demand. Diversifying crops can reduce water consumption and mitigate risks associated with relying solely on paddy. Growing a variety of crops enables farmers to tap into different market opportunities and increase income stability. Farmers should also be made aware of market vulnerabilities and the importance of understanding supply and demand dynamics. Access to information on market trends, consumer preferences, and price fluctuations enables informed decision-making. This knowledge empowers farmers to align their crop choices and production strategies with market demands, maximizing profitability.

Government agencies, agricultural extension services, and NGOs play a vital role in providing farmers with training and support. Workshops, training programs, and information-sharing platforms can educate farmers about sustainable practices, crop diversification, and market intelligence. Financial incentives and agricultural loans can further encourage farmers to adopt new practices and invest in alternative crops. By promoting behavioral change and equipping farmers with knowledge and resources to adapt to market vulnerabilities, we can create a more resilient and sustainable agricultural sector. This shift towards diversified and market-oriented farming practices benefits individual farmers and contributes to rural development, poverty reduction, and environmental conservation. Recognizing the interconnectedness of agriculture, market dynamics, and sustainable development is crucial for long-term prosperity in farming communities.

2. Market linkages

The need to focus on market linkages in agricultural policies is essential to address the shortcomings of an overly production-centric approach. Historically, agricultural policies have placed excessive emphasis on increasing production without adequately considering the market dynamics and the needs of consumers and agribusinesses. A shift in perspective is required to align agricultural policies with market realities. Instead of solely concentrating on production targets, policymakers must emphasize the development of robust market linkages that connect farmers with consumers, processors, and other stakeholders in the value chain. This approach ensures that agricultural production is demand-driven and responsive to market signals.

By fostering stronger market linkages, farmers can gain better access to markets, receive fair prices for their produce, and reduce post-harvest losses. Market-oriented policies also encourage farmers to diversify their crops and produce high-value agricultural commodities that have a strong demand in domestic and international markets. This diversification reduces the vulnerability of farmers to price fluctuations and market uncertainties associated with a narrow focus on a single crop. To achieve effective market linkages, policymakers should invest in infrastructure development, such as storage facilities, transportation networks, and market information systems. These initiatives enable efficient

movement of agricultural produce from farms to consumers, enhance market transparency, and enable farmers to make informed decisions about crop selection and pricing strategies.

Moreover, capacity-building programs and training initiatives should be implemented to equip farmers with the knowledge and skills necessary to understand market trends, negotiate fair contracts, and adopt market-oriented farming practices. Farmers' access to market intelligence, credit facilities, and value-added processing technologies should also be improved to enhance their competitiveness in the marketplace. By shifting the focus of agricultural policies from mere production to strong market linkages, policymakers in Telangana can create an enabling environment for farmers to thrive in a demand-driven agricultural economy. This approach ensures sustainable agricultural growth, enhances farmers' incomes, and promotes overall rural development.

3. Cost recovery and public finance

Addressing the issue of cost recovery and the unsustainable electricity bill in the project requires careful consideration and a strategic roadmap. Here are some key steps that can be taken to tackle this challenge.

Firstly, conducting a comprehensive financial analysis of the project is essential to understand the cost structure and identify areas where cost reduction is possible. This analysis should include a detailed assessment of the project's operational expenses, maintenance costs, and interest payments. By identifying areas of inefficiency and implementing cost-saving measures, such as optimizing energy usage and exploring alternative energy sources, the project can significantly reduce its electricity bill.

Secondly, exploring revenue-generation opportunities can contribute to cost recovery. This can involve diversifying the project's income streams by exploring additional services or products that can be offered. For instance, the project can explore opportunities for selling excess electricity generated through renewable sources to the grid, providing a potential revenue source to offset the electricity bill. Furthermore, forging strategic partnerships and collaborations with relevant stakeholders can help share the financial burden. Engaging with government agencies, private sector organizations, or international development partners can provide access to funding or investment opportunities that can support cost recovery efforts.

Additionally, implementing user fees or tariffs can be considered to ensure that beneficiaries or users of the project contribute to its financial sustainability. This approach ensures a fair distribution of costs and encourages responsible usage of project resources. Lastly, continuous monitoring and evaluation of the project's financial performance is crucial to assessing the effectiveness of cost recovery measures and making necessary adjustments. This includes regular reviews of the project's financial sustainability plan and exploring innovative financing mechanisms that align with the project's objectives.

Addressing the challenge of cost recovery and the unsustainable electricity bill requires a comprehensive approach that includes optimizing costs, diversifying revenue streams, fostering partnerships, and implementing appropriate financing mechanisms. By adopting a strategic roadmap and implementing these measures, the project can work towards achieving financial sustainability in the long run.

Overall, the success of the Kaleshwaram project is also due to a strong political will to achieve something phenomenal for the newly carved state of Telangana. The polity strongly believed that access to water for all would create a strong base for a stronger future. As Hoover dam transformed the Californian desert into one of the most productive and fast-growing regions in the world, Kaleshwaram could do the same for the State of Telangana. It is indeed the responsibility of those who have most benefited from this process to support and strengthen those who have lost in the tradeoff.

Annexure I

Comparing Land Acquisition Act of 2013 with Land Acquisition Bill of 2015

Issue	Land Acquisition Act 2013	Land Acquisition (Second Amendment Bill, 2015
Consent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ No consent is required for government projects. ▶ Consent of 70% of landowners is required for Public-Private Partnership projects. ▶ Consent of 80% of landowners is required for private projects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Five types of projects exempt from consent requirements: (i) defence, (ii) rural infrastructure, (iii) affordable housing, (iv) industrial corridors set up by the government/government undertakings, up to one km on either side of the road/railway of the corridor, and (v) infrastructure including PPP projects where the government owns the land.
Social Impact Assessment (SIA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ SIA is mandatory for all projects except: (i) in cases of urgency or (ii) for irrigation projects where an Environmental Impact Assessment is required. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ The government may exempt above five types of projects from SIA. ▶ The government is to ensure that the extent of land being acquired is in keeping with the minimum land required.
Irrigated multi-cropped land	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Irrigated multi-cropped land cannot be acquired beyond a limit specified by the state government. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ The government may exempt the above five types of projects from this provision. • The government is to ensure that the extent of land being acquired is in keeping with the minimum land required.
Compensation & rehabilitation and resettlement (R&R) provisions of 13 other laws which govern land acquisition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ 13 Acts (such as the National Highways Act, 1956 and the Railways Act, 1989) are exempt from the provisions of the Act. ▶ The compensation and R&R provisions of these Acts to be brought in consonance with the Act by January 1, 2015. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Compensation and R&R provisions of 13 Acts are in consonance with the Act.

Issue	Land Acquisition Act 2013	Land Acquisition (Second Amendment) Bill, 2015
Offences by the government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ If an offence is committed by a government department, the head of the department will be deemed guilty unless he can show that he had exercised due diligence to prevent the commission of the offence. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ The Bill deletes this provision. ▶ The Bill adds a provision to state that prior sanction of the government will be required before prosecuting a government employee.
Retrospective application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ The 2013 Act will apply in case an award has been made five years or more before the commencement of the 2013 Act, but the physical possession of the land has not been taken or compensation has not been paid. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ In calculating the time period for retrospective application, any period during which the proceedings were held up: (i) due to a stay order of a court, or (ii) for a period specified in the award of a Tribunal, or (iii) for any period where possession was taken but the compensation is lying deposited in a court or any designated account, will not be counted.
Return of unutilised land	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ If land acquired under the Act remains unutilised for five years from the date of taking possession, it must be returned to the original owners or a land bank. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ The period after which unutilised land has to be returned will be the later of: (i) five years, or (ii) any period specified at the time of setting up the project.
Change from private 'company' to private 'entity'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Private company defined as one included in the Companies Act, 1956, or under the Societies Registration Act, 1860. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ The term 'private company' changed to 'private entity' which is defined as an entity other than a government entity, and includes a proprietorship, partnership, company, corporation, non-profit etc.
Rehabilitation & Resettlement award	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Includes employment to one member of an affected family. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Clarifies that this will include employment to 'one member of such affected family of farm labour' must be given.

Issue	Land Acquisition Act 2013	Land Acquisition (Second Amendment Bill, 2015
Land Acquisition, Rehabilitation and Resettlement Authority	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ In case someone is not satisfied with an award under the Act, they can approach the Land Acquisition, Rehabilitation and Resettlement (LARR) Authority. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Adds that the LARR Authority must hold its hearing in the district where land acquisition is taking place, after a reference from the Collector and giving notice to all concerned parties.
Survey of wasteland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ No provision 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ The government must conduct a survey of its wasteland and maintain a record of the same.

Source: Ministry of Rural Development, 2013.

Annexure II

Statutory Clearances for Kaleshwaram Project

S.No.	Name of Directorate/Ministry/Board	Status of Clearance
1	Hydrology (S)	Clearance received from CWC vide Lr.F.No.6/231/2017-PA (S) / 1327 – 28, dt. 30.10.2017
2	Inter-State Matters (ISM)	Clearance received from CWC vide Lr.No. U.No. 4/2/TEL./ISM-I/2017/927-928, Dt: 03-11-2017 & Lr.No. U.No.4/2/TEL./ISM-I/2017/974
3	Construction Machinery Consultancy (CMC)	Clearance Received from CWC vide U.O.No.21/Telangana/02/2017-CMC/432, dt.24.11.2017
4	Irrigation Planning (S)	Clearance Received CWC ID No. 2/148/IP (S)/2013/272 Dt. 13.04.2018 and BC Ratio finalized vide CWC ID No.2/1481/IP (S)/2013/320 Dt: 11.05.2018
5	Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare (MoA&FW), Govt. of India	Clearance Received CWC ID No. 2/148/IP (S)/2013/272 Dt. 13.04.2018 and BC Ratio finalized vide CWC ID No.2/1481/IP (S)/2013/320 Dt: 11.05.2018
6	Cost Appraisal (I)	Finalized Cost Received from CWC vide ID No.10-A/27/2017/CA(I)-2/77, Dt. 01.05.2018
7	Central Soil & Materials Research Station (CSMRS)	Clearance Received from CSMRS vide U.O No. 26/36/Kaleshwaram/RM-I/CSMRS/2017/308 dt. 21.05.2018
8	Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change (MoEF&CC)	1) <i>Environmental Clearance:</i> Environmental Clearance Received from MoEF vide Lr.No.1-12011/1/2017-IA-I (R) Dt. 22.12.2017 2) <i>Forest Clearance:</i> Stage-I Clearance received from MoEF vide F.No. 8-31/2017-FC Dt. 24-10.2017 Stage-II Clearance received from MoEF vide F.No 8-31/2017-FC Dt. 24.11.2017
9	Central Ground Water Board (CGWB)	Clearance received vide Lr. No: 4-1/CWC-PA/SML-CGWB/2017-1945, Dt. 21.11.2017
10	Technical Advisory Committee (TAC)	Acceptance of Kaleshwaram Project in he 136th TAC Meeting held on 06.06.2018 communicated by CWC through Minutes vide Lr. No. 16/27/2018-PA(N)/939-70, Dt: 14.06.2018

Source: Department of Irrigation & CAD, Government of Telangana, 2022

Annexure III

Impact of Kaleshwaram on Crop Production

Annappurna Reservoir Command Area Change in Crop Sown Area

Season/Year	Kharif 2018-19	Rabi 2018-19	Kharif 2019-20	Rabi 2019-20	Kharif 2020-21	Rabi 2020-21	Kharif 2021-22	Rabi 2021-22
Area (acre) Wet	7538	5506	12688	5305	16646	16646	13931	13713
Area (acre) Dry	24581	1852	19127	8244	15655	1734	17770	4951
Area (acre) Fallow		24760		18265		13920	95	13132

Ranganayaka Sagar Reservoir Command Area Change in Crop Sown Area

Season/Year	Kharif 2018-19	Rabi 2018-19	Kharif 2019-20	Rabi 2019-20	Kharif 2020-21	Rabi 2020-21	Kharif 2021-22	Rabi 2021-22
Area (acre) Wet	13298	13284	43673	43673	61462	61750	67406	57849
Area (acre) Dry	23635	2915	46925	3790	33672	4843	29004	5963
Area (acre) Fallow	41968	62698		43134	288	28829	1023	33621

Mallanna Sagar Reservoir Command Area Change in crop Sown Area

Season/Year	Kharif 2018-19	Rabi 2018-19	Kharif 2019-20	Rabi 2019-20	Kharif 2020-21	Rabi 2020-21	Kharif 2021-22	Rabi 2021-22
Area (acre) Wet	28050	12901	43158	39235	62857	59958	64634	56141
Area (acre) Dry	42937	5772	45985	4362	23851	3547	17090	5408
Area (acre) Fallow		52324		45431	1351	24478	1289	21163

Source: Department of Irrigation & CAD

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